

Certificate of Calibration

OPTICAL DEW-POINT HYGROMETER
18-0719

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FOR: University of Leeds
FAAM Airborne Laboratory
Building 85
Cranfield University
Bedford
MK43 0JR

For the attention of Jack Farr

IDENTIFICATION: Optical dew-point hygrometer
Model: MBW 973L
Serial No: 18-0719
Software: MBW GeckoR2 V0.9.7

**PREVIOUS
CERTIFICATE:** 2021050317 dated 7 July 2021

**DATES OF
CALIBRATION:** 29 September 2022 to 6 October 2022

Reference: 2022060331

Date of issue: 7 October 2022

Checked by: *K Douglas*

Signed:

Name: Mr P A Carroll

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(Authorised Signatory)

on behalf of NPLML

This certificate is consistent with the capabilities that are included in Appendix C of the MRA drawn up by the CIPM. Under the MRA, all participating institutes recognise the validity of each other's calibration and measurement certificates for the quantities, ranges and measurement uncertainties specified in Appendix C (for details see <http://www.bipm.org>).

MEASUREMENTS

The test hygrometer is equipped with a digital display and RS232 output. The "Mirror Temperature" of the RS232 output was logged and these values appear in the table below.

The calibration was carried out against NPL Standard Humidity Generators, in terms of dew-point temperature. The "generated dew point" was determined from measurements made using platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs). Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of these thermometers to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) through NPL Temperature Standards.

Before use, the hygrometer mirror was cleaned successively with isopropyl alcohol, deionised water and then again with isopropyl alcohol using cotton buds. Following each cleaning the mirror enclosure was dried in a stream of clean dry air.

Air of a known dew-point temperature, at a pressure of 105.0 kPa, was supplied to the test hygrometer inlet. At dew-point temperatures below 0 °C a 1.3 m length of 3 mm internal diameter stainless steel tubing was used. At dew-point temperatures above 0 °C a 1.2 m length of 4 mm internal diameter PTFE tubing was used. The moist air was then vented to atmosphere, through a rotameter with a needle valve assembly for flow control. The air flow rate was set so that the flow through the test hygrometer was nominally 0.5 litres per minute, as measured by an additional rotameter on the exhaust of the hygrometer.

The measurement procedure was as follows:

- a) the temperature of the thermostatically controlled NPL Generator bath containing a primed saturator was set
- b) air was circulated through the pipework and the NPL Generator system was allowed to come to equilibrium
- c) the hygrometer mirror was cleared of condensate which was then allowed to re-form
- d) the RS232 output of the test hygrometer was monitored until the instrument was seen to have stabilised.

At the conclusion of the final step of the above procedure a set of ten readings was then taken over a period of at least 20 minutes.

The ambient conditions in the NPL humidity laboratory were 23 °C ± 3 °C and less than 80 % relative humidity.

NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY

Continuation Sheet

RESULTS

The results of the calibration are given in the table below. Each value of the generated dew-point temperature is quoted with its expanded uncertainty. The test hygrometer results quote the mean and the standard deviation of ten readings for that instrument. The values in the final column show the expanded uncertainty of the measurement. This quoted uncertainty relates to the period of the calibration and is not an indication of the long-term stability of the instrument.

Generated Dew Point		Test Hygrometer		
Temperature	Expanded Uncertainty of Generated Dew Point	Logged Mirror Temperature	Standard Deviation	Expanded Uncertainty of Measurement
°C	°C	°C	°C	°C
-70.00	0.06	-69.72	0.010	0.11
-59.99	0.03	-59.96	0.013	0.04
-50.12	0.03	-50.15	0.019	0.04
-30.07	0.03	-30.11	0.007	0.04
-10.19	0.03	-10.22	0.002	0.04
+0.95	0.03	+0.94	0.011	0.04
+9.96	0.03	+9.97	0.003	0.04
+20.02	0.03	+20.04	0.005	0.04

UNCERTAINTIES

The standard uncertainty of the generated dew point is calculated by combining the estimated uncertainties arising from the calibration, drift, self heating and measurement of the PRTs, the saturation efficiency, temperature conditioning and pressure variations of the NPL Generator, the temperature variations in the generator bath and the effects of leaks, desorption and contamination.

The standard uncertainty of measurement is calculated by combining the standard uncertainties of the generated dew point, the standard deviation of the recorded readings of the instrument, its resolution and an estimate of its reproducibility during calibration. An uncertainty contribution has been included for rounding to give results an equivalent resolution of 0.01 °C.

The expanded uncertainty is based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$, providing a coverage probability of approximately 95%. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.

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